

The Dielectric Constant of Methylene Chloride and Methylene Bromide.

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It is a well-known experimental fact that the dielectric constant of molecules having symmetrical structures is independent of temperature whereas the polar molecules having asymmetric constitution indicate a diminution of the dielectric constant with rise in temperature.

The theoretical aspect of this phenomenon was investigated by Debye (*Phys. Zeit.*, 1921, 13, 97), J. J. Thomson (*Phil. Mag.*, 1924, 27, 757), and Gans (*Ann. Physik*, 1921, 65, vi, 481) on classical consideration. Pauli (*Zeit. Physik*, 1921, 6, 319), and Manneback (*Phys. Zeit.*, 1926, 27, 568; 1927, 28, -72) treated the same from the standpoint of classical quantum theory and wave-mechanics.

Considering that the molecules of gases and vapours are polarised in an electric field and that the polarisation field acting on the molecules is isotropic in character, Debye deduced the following expression for the dielectric constant of molecules which are unaffected by temperature,

$$\frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{\rho} = \frac{4\pi}{3} \cdot 4N\gamma \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where

ϵ = Dielectric constant;

M = Molecular weight;

ρ = Density;

N = Avogadro's number;

γ = Polarisability of the molecule.

For molecules whose dielectric constant is affected by variation in temperature, Debye assumed that they develop a permanent dipole having a fixed direction with reference to the molecule. Assuming that the distribution of molecules is regulated by the well known Boltzmann—Maxwell distribution law with temperature, the contribution of these permanent dipole moments to the dielectric constant can be expressed by the expression

$$\frac{4\pi}{9} \cdot \frac{\mu^2 N}{KT} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where μ = Moment of the dipole;

K = Boltzmann constant;

T = Absolute temperature.

Thus the complete expression for the dielectric constant is

$$\frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{\rho} = \frac{4\pi N}{3} \left(v + \frac{\mu^2}{3kT} \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Since in gases ϵ differs by a very small amount from unity, we can put $\epsilon + 2 = 3$.

$$\text{Hence } \frac{\epsilon - 1}{\rho} \cdot MT = 4\pi N \gamma T + \frac{4\pi N}{3k} \cdot \mu^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Further assuming that gases and vapours in unsaturated state obey the simple gas laws and noting that

$$\frac{\rho_0}{M} = \frac{1}{22.4 \times 10^3} \text{ gm.,}$$

$$\text{we get } \frac{(\epsilon - 1) P_0 T^2}{P} = a v T + b \mu^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

$$\text{where } a = \frac{4\pi N_o T}{22.4 \times 10^3} \quad b = \frac{4\pi N T_o}{3k \times 22.4 \times 10^3}$$

The expression (5) giving a direct method of ascertaining the magnitude of the polarisability ν of the molecule as well as the magnitude of the dipole moment μ in the molecule.

Thus drawing a graph with T and $\frac{(\epsilon-1) P_o T^2}{P}$ as x and y axes,

the slope of the line will be the value of $a\nu$ and the intercept at the origin of co-ordinates will give the value of $b\mu^2$.

On the basis of the above formula, Zahn (*Phys. Rev.*, 1924, 23, 345), Watson (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1927, 117, 43), Braunmühl (*Phys. Zeit.*, 1927, 28, 141), Sanger (*Phys. Zeit.*, 1926, 27, 556), and Maske (*Phys. Zeit.*, 1927, 28, 553) have determined the dielectric constant and dipole moment of several gases and vapours. Rieger (*Ann. Physik*, 1919, 59, viii, 753) and Zahn and Smyth (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 2501) together also investigated into the relation between the unsaturated bonds of organic molecules and their dielectric constant.

The nature of change of the polarisability and dipole moments of some of the ethyl and methyl halides has been investigated by the present authors (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1928, 3, 181). It is seen that the polarisability of these halides increases as we pass from the chlorides to the iodides whereas the permanent dipole moment diminishes. In the present paper the authors propose to determine the polarisability and the dipole moment of the symmetrical molecule CH_2Cl_2 when two of its hydrogen atoms are replaced by halogen atoms.

The dipole moment of CH_2Cl_2 has already been determined by Sanger (*loc. cit.*) by a method differing in technique from that of the present authors, who, therefore, have repeated his observations on CH_2Cl_2 and measured the polarisability and dipole moment of CH_2Br_2 , thus getting these values for the two methylene halides under the same arrangement which the authors have developed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement is the same as has been adopted in a previous investigation (*loc. cit.*), *viz.*, that of the heterodyne beat method when two oscillating circuits, as shown in Figure 1, of

Fig. 1.

frequencies 1.5×10^6 and 1.501024×10^6 respectively are loosely coupled to produce a beat tone of 1024 frequency. The beat tone is adjusted in unison with a valve maintained tuning fork of 1024 frequency. The experimental gas condenser *c* is put in series with a standard precision variable vernier condenser *K*, which is in parallel with a fixed condenser, *K'*, of the Dubilier type. The methods of adjustment and the calibration of the condensers used are described in detail in the above paper.

The chemicals used were brought from Schuchardt.

Results.

TABLE I.

Methylene Chloride, b.p. 41°.

T°.	($\epsilon-1$)760	$\frac{(\epsilon-1)P_0T^2}{P}$
308°0	·007076	649
332°5	·005920	655
390°0	·004869	664
426°0	·008684	672

Methylene Bromide, b. p. 81°.

T°.	($\epsilon-1$)760	$\frac{(\epsilon-1)P_0T^2}{P}$
322°0	·008808	912
357°0	·007248	924
388°0	·006177	930
420°0	·005329	940

TABLE II.

Vapour.	($\epsilon-1$).	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
CH ₂ Cl ₂	·0006890	1·621
CH ₂ Br ₂	·0009947	1·914

A graph showing the relation between $\frac{(\epsilon-1)P_0T^2}{P}$ and T^0 is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2.

Discussion.

It has been pointed out in a previous paper (*loc. cit.*) that a symmetrical molecule of the type of CH_4 and C_2H_6 get their symmetry disturbed by the substitution of a single atom of hydrogen by a halogen atom. It was further pointed out that the polarisability of the molecule is increased when Br is substituted for Cl and I is substituted for Br. On the other hand the dipole moment of RCl is greater than that of RBr and that of RBr greater than that of RI , R standing for the CH_4 or C_2H_6 group.

The nature of polar molecules has been investigated by Born Debye and others from the behaviour of ions in solution and of

crystalline solids composed of solid ions in aggregation. One can assume that polar molecules are composed of positive and negative ions held together by electrostatic forces and there may be a transfer of one or more electrons from one atom to another. In the majority of polar molecules it is reasonable to picture the model as composed of ions whose individual atoms retain their own electronic orbits and the attractive force between the ions is balanced by the force of repulsion between their electronic shells. Lewis and Langmuir from a large number of instances consider the model as that of atoms consisting of rigid shell of eight electrons and the outer valency electrons forming a link which keeps the stability of the molecules. Fajans and Joos (*Zeit. Physik*, 1924, 23, 1) investigated the polarisability of the electronic shell from the viewpoint of dispersion. Born and Heisenberg (*Zeit. Physik*, 1924, 23, 388) treated the same subject in the case of alkali halides in solution and considered that this molecular polarisability can be deduced from the consideration of the deformation of the electron orbits according to the spectroscopic standpoint. The molecular structure has their electronic shells participating in a fashion as to form an inert gas configuration. The polarisability as deduced from dispersion measurements of Wasastijerna (*Comm. Fernn.*, 1913, 1, 7) of dilute solutions of the salts is in fair agreement with the data from the rare gases.

To form a mental picture of the formation of the molecules of the type having a positively charged organic radicle and a negatively charged halogen ion, it is easy to conceive that they will attract each other and the formation of a stable molecule requires a force of repulsion at short distance to balance this force of attraction. The origin of this force of repulsion is well known in the case of simple polar halides like HCl where the H^+ nucleus enters a region in which the outermost electron no longer attracts it so strongly and the repulsive force between the nuclei balances the nett attractive force of the electron swarm and H^+ ion thus forming the stable HCl molecule. This hypothesis is tenable in view of the small size of H^+ ion.

In the case of organic halides formed of the CH_3^+ and Cl^- ions however, such a penetration of CH_3^+ inside the electronic boundary of Cl^- would involve an apparently hopeless distortion of both the electron orbits. Hence it would be more reasonable to assume that each retains its own electron orbits and the electron spheres would

not interpenetrate some other source of repulsion is to be sought to explain the formation of such a stable molecule. Debye (*Zeit. Physik*, 1921, 22, 302) has suggested an origin of this force. He first discusses the formation of a negative ion and calls attention to the fact that if a free electron is brought near an atom, *i.e.*, an electron rotating in an orbit about a nucleus, the free electron will tend to execute forced oscillations with the period of the orbital electron, which would slow down on its approach to the free electron and the time average of the repulsive force will be increased. The same considerations would lead to similar repulsion acting when an atom approaches an atom or a positively charged ion approaches an atom.

Now let us suppose that when Cl^- ion approaches a positive radicle such as CH_3^+ , the loosely bound electron of the negative ion would take up an orbit encircling both the Cl atom and the CH_3^+ radicle. The repulsive force between the Cl nucleus and the nuclei of the CH_3^+ together with the repulsive force of the orbital electron of Cl^- and the orbital electron of CH_3^+ would balance the attractive force of the electron swarm of Cl^- and the CH_3^+ radicle and the stable CH_3Cl molecule is formed.

In the case of the molecules CH_2Cl_2 and CH_2Br_2 , the two loosely bound electrons of the negatively charged halogen ions would encircle the system and the above considered mutual forces would lead to the formation of the molecules.

It is further known that CH_4 can be regarded as having the structure of a symmetrical tetrahedron with C atom at its centre of gravity (Dennison, *Astro. J.*, 1925, 62, 84). The CH_2Cl_2 molecule may be regarded as a distorted tetrahedron with the Cl atoms at its two corners. Due to the interaction of the electronic orbits the orbits of Cl atoms as well as that of CH_2^{++} will be distorted. These distortions will develop moments in the two Cl atoms as well as in the CH_2^{++} ion. The direction of the moments in the two Cl atoms will be mutually inclined to each other and the moment of CH_2^{++} will be making equal angles with the direction of the moments in each Cl atom. The moments of Cl atoms will however partly neutralise each other due to their inclinations and the nett permanent moment of the molecule is the resultant of the moment of the CH_2^{++} ion and the resolved part of the moments of the Cl atoms operating in the opposite direction.

When Br is substituted in place of Cl, the Br nuclei come in closer proximity to the C-nucleus and owing to the larger nuclear charge of Br they are mutually separated from each other to a larger extent than in the case of Cl atoms. The two electrons surrounding the system are more rigidly bound to it than in the case of CH_2Cl_2 . Their orbits are thus less distorted and hence CH_2Br_2 has a larger polarisability than CH_2Cl_2 . This increase of polarisability evidently indicates a greater cohesive force acting inside the molecule and the boiling point of CH_2Br_2 is therefore higher than that of CH_2Cl_2 . This greater polarisability also accounts for the smaller interatomic forces to form the molecule leading to low stability. Hence CH_2Cl_2 is more stable than CH_2Br_2 .

Now when we consider the permanent dipole moment of CH_2^-Br_2 , we notice that the two Br atoms are more inclined to each other than in the case of Cl atoms and the resultant of the resolved part of their moments acting in the direction opposite to that of the moment developed in the CH_2^{++} ion will be less than in the case of Cl atoms. The nett dipole moment of CH_2Br_2 is thus greater than that of CH_2Cl_2 .

The authors expect a still higher polarisability and a greater dipole moment in the case of CH_2I_2 but technical difficulties stand in the way to its measurement, partly because the vapour pressure of CH_2I_2 is very low at the room temperature and also that the CH_2I_2 decomposes at ordinary temperatures under normal pressure. The boiling point of CH_2I_2 is about 130° . With the present arrangement only those liquids that have boiling points below 100° can be studied.

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